

THE SUPREME COUNCIL AND ITS ROLE IN THE CENTRAL MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN THE KOKAN KHANATE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8005170>

Annotation: The Kokan Khanate, though short in history, played a major role in the political, socio-economic and cultural life of the peoples of Central Asia. Although this khanate was similar to other Central Asian khanates with many features of the state structure, there were sharp differences in the functions of the persons responsible for managing the state and some links of the management system. Also, studying one of the important issues of Uzbek statehood - the history of the administrative-management system of the Kokan khanate within the periodical boundary of the beginning of the 18th century and the third quarter of the 19th century - makes the topic relevant.

Key words and expressions: supreme council, okan Khanate, central administration, management system, various positions, duties of officials, advisory body, foreign policy, military affairs, Emirate of Bukhara, advisory body.

After the Timurids in Central Asia, the system of state administration began to change during the reign of the Shaibanis. If we look at the central administrative system of the dynasties before the Shaybanites, it can be observed that it consisted of a dargah and a divan. Dargah - the ruling chief was the highest state office, and devans were considered ministries that managed tasks in a certain area. It is clearly visible that such a system of management, brought to a perfect order, completely changed in the Bukhara Khanate by the time of the Ashtarkhanids. In the words of Azamat Zia, during this period, "... this system (dargahs and devans) disappeared and executive duties were embodied directly in one or another position in the palace or in the activities of some personage."¹ Therefore, the activity of the devans was put to an end by assigning the duties of the special ministries, where different officials were working, to a single person. This situation is also observed in other Central Asian countries. In particular, during this period, the state administration of the Khanate of Khiva was carried out in this way.²

The same system was formed in the state administration of the Kokan Khanate, which was created due to the weakening of the rule of the Ashtarkhanid dynasty in the Bukhara Khanate. Information from historical sources made it possible to determine the following about the central management system formed in the Kokan Khanate. In the Kokan Khanate, the seat of government was located in the khan's court, and all matters of state importance were decided in this palace. The central management system was fully embodied in the Horde, and all the officials working in it were included in the Supreme Council headed by the Khan. The central government consisted of a supreme ruler, then a council, which was an advisory body, and then officials in charge of executive functions.

¹ Зиё А. Ўзбек давлатчилиги тарихи... - Б. 295.

² Йўлдошев М. Хива хонлигида феодал ер эгалиги ва давлат тузилиши. - Т.: 1959.

The state carried out its internal and external policy, leading relations with the society, relying on a complex management body that was formed and perfected over the centuries. This body is the High Council under the rulers of Central Asian khanates, and in historical sources it is expressed by such words as "council", "special council", "mashvarat", "majlisi sultanyi".

Russian officers, ambassadors and tourists who were in the khanate in the 19th century, and local authors wrote down important information about the council under the Kokan rulers. In 1813-1814, the translator of the Siberian Corps, who was in Kokan, F. In his memoirs, Nazarov describes an interesting situation that serves to imagine the council. According to him, "a number of ministers and state officials, who make up the supreme council of the ruler, sat according to their rank on the carpets placed next to the throne."³

This information given by F. Nazarov about the council is a general characteristic not only of the Kokand Khanate, but also of other states that existed in Central Asia at that time.

Speaking about the composition of the Supreme Council of the Kokan Khanate, it should be noted that all the officials of the central state administration were included in its composition. According to historical sources, the prime minister of the Kokan khanate, the thousandbashi and the highest religious official, was a permanent member of the council. Also, the chief judge of the khanate, that is, two judges on military affairs and military judges, also participated in the council. V. V. Velyaminov-Zernov notes in his work that by the 30s of the 19th century, the waiter and pamphleteer, who were among the important tasks in the central state administration, were also members of the council.⁴

According to the 19th century researcher V. Grigorev, during the first reign of Khudoyor Khan, the council consisted of four kipchaks.⁵ After putting the young Khudoyar Khan on the throne, Muslim got the title of father and took full control of the state. He strengthened his rule by appointing the Kipchaks to important positions in the central state administration, such as a waiter, waiter, pamphleteer. Local sources provide information about Muhammad Diyar, Mullo Holbek tableau, and Rahmonquli dodhohs, who were the leaders of the Kipchaks in the central state administration during the period when Muslimquli took power in 1845. So, it can be seen that in the early years of Khudoyar Khan's reign, Muslimkuli held a council with these officials. According to historical sources, by the 60s of the XIX century, the council was expanded, and 12 officials from the central state administration were included in the council.⁶

These data show that the members of the council, their number and composition changed during each ruler of the Kokan Khanate. The reasons for this could be different. The above situation is observed in cases where all the power is concentrated in the hands of a single guardian, including when a person like the Muslim chief holds the power in his hands for a long time. They used strict management methods and limited the authority of the central governing body as an advisory body. This situation allowed them to rule the country in an

³ Назаров Ф. Записки о некотором народах и землях средней части Азии / Текст подготовил В.А. Ромодин. - М.: Наука, 1968. - С. 41.

⁴ Вельямнов-Зернов В.В. Исторические известия о Кокандском ханстве от Мухаммед-Али до Худаярхана. - СПб. 1856. - С. 20

⁵ Григорьев В.В. Современне монетм Кокандского ханства // Трудм Восточного отделения императорского археологического общества. 1856. Вмп. 2. Ч. 2 - СПб. - С. 116.

⁶ Кокандское ханство по новейшим известиям // Туркестанский сборник, Т. 23. - С.65.

authoritarian manner. Also, this situation has led to confrontation and struggle of political forces, various forms of protests of the population.⁷

The analysis of historical data shows that sometimes when officials such as koshbegi or parvanachi, who occupied important positions in the central administration of the khanate, were appointed governors of a region, their seats in the Supreme Council under the Supreme Ruler were temporarily vacant. In such cases, their duties were performed by one official, that is, he was entrusted with the performance of two types of duties.

One of the important aspects of statehood is to satisfy the material and spiritual needs of citizens, raise the potential of the state and develop it in all aspects, and establish economic and political diplomatic relations with foreign or neighboring countries. The rulers tried to carry out positive reforms in the state administration. The advice of potential officials in matters of socio-economic, political, cultural-educational life and foreign relations of the state is of great importance for the rulers.

Regarding the activity of the council under the rulers of Kokan, that is, what issues were discussed in it, some clarifications can be made based on some information available in the works of local historians. The work "History of Turkestan" provides the following information: "[Olimkhan] invited many scholars and fuzals to the gathering, held a special meeting, asked the goddess about the situation of the army and the condition of the enemy, the repulsion of the enemy, the peace of Ferghana and the peace of the country, and the advice about the country itself. did..."⁸ Another information about Kokan rulers' consultation with the council on some issues can be found in Avaz Muhammad Attar's "History of Jahonnamoyi". According to him, after Shahrisabz, a province of Bukhara Emirate, was conquered by the Russian Empire, its governor Bobobek went to Kokan. Hearing this news, Khudoyor Khan is in a difficult situation and consults with officials in the central administration system about whether to leave Bobobek in Kok or send him to Kashgar.⁹

In the Kokan Khanate, as in the Bukhara Emirate and the Khiva Khanate, the Supreme Ruler - Khan stood at the head of power and was considered the central figure of the High Council. It is known from history that the supreme rulership could pass from father to son, from brother to brother or to a relative. Nevertheless, in the appointment of a new ruler, the influence of the representatives of the ruling circle, as well as the council, was strong. At this point, it should be noted that the appointment of various persons to the administrative system of the state in the Kokan khanate, the ceremonies and ceremonies held at the time of their appointment to these positions are also related to the ancient traditions of Uzbek statehood. One of the ceremonies that took an important place in the administration of the state was the ceremony of appointing the supreme ruler, that is, "raising the khan", this ceremony had its own characteristics.

The analyzed historical data show that the rulers of Kokand relied on their internal and external policy on a special consultative body - the High Council, that this body was formed and developed since the founding of the khanate, that its activity rose to a higher level in certain historical periods and conditions, or that it strongly used authoritarian methods of rule. and during the period of the rulers, the range of opportunities became narrower, and it shows that certain changes took place in its composition. The presence of the Oliy kanesh, an

⁷Набиев Р.Н. Из истории Кокандского ханства... - С. 39 - 45.

⁸ Мулло Олим Махдум Ҳожи. Тарихи Туркистон... - Б. 29.

⁹ Аваз Мухаммад Аттот. Тарихи Жаҳоннамойи // Шарқ юлдузи. 1991. - № 8. - Б. 137.

advisory body in the khanate management system, shows that the rulers of Kokand tried to manage the khanate on the basis of historical succession and the traditions of Uzbek statehood.

As a result of the unique political, socio-economic processes in the Ferghana Valley in Central Asia, as well as the weakening of the political leadership and the potential of the centralized state observed in the Ashtarkhanid state at the beginning of the 18th century, this region was politically separated from the Bukhara Khanate. In this process, the leaders of the thousand clan took advantage of the situation, and the clan elder Shahrukhbiy (1709-1721) founded a new state.

In the Kokan Khanate, a system of central and local administration was formed based on the traditions of statehood developed in Central Asia. Statehood in Central Asia - a simple style of management that incorporates traditions such as the central and local management system, which was fully implemented in the Bukhara khanate during the Ashtarkhanid era, was also used in the Kokan khanate. The 90 years covering the period from the first decade of the 18th century to the beginning of the 19th century, when the Khanate was established, should be considered as the period of formation of the administrative-management system, which is one of the important components of statehood in Kok. During this period, there were almost no changes in the khanate administrative management system, formed on the basis of the traditions existing in Central Asia. Only at the beginning of the new century, changes were made in this regard. This includes the activities carried out by Olim Khan (1798-1810) and his brother Umar Khan (1810-1822), who ascended the throne after Norbotabi, in order to increase the political status of the state, strengthen the potential of the centralized state, the military reforms they carried out, and the domestic and foreign policy aimed at further expanding the territory of the country. created During this period, new positions such as mingbashi, khojakalon, qaziaskar were introduced in the central management system of the state.

From the 40s of the 19th century, the period of crisis of the Kokan Khanate began. This was caused by the continuous struggle for the throne between different groups, and the interference of foreign countries, in particular, the Bukhara Emirate, in the internal politics of the khanate. Also, his father-in-law, a Kipchak Muslim centurion who took advantage of Khudoyor Khan's youth and became the regent of the Supreme Ruler, gave important tasks to his clansmen in the central and local administration, which led to the displeasure of other ethnic groups. This, in turn, serves as one of the internal factors that ensured the further confusion of political life in the khanate and the crisis of the management system.

In the khanates of Central Asia, in particular, in the Khanate of Kokand, the simplification of the administrative and management system can be observed at the end of the 18th century and the 70s of the 19th centuries. By this time, the dargahs and devans, which are its main links, were almost non-functional. The tasks assigned to these structures, which are an important component of the state management system, become the main content of the activities of some officials. At the same time, state management was carried out relying on the consultative body that replaced them - the Supreme Council. The rulers of Kokand conducted their domestic and foreign policy relying on this body. The activity of this consultative body increased in certain historical periods and conditions, or in periods when the arbitrariness of certain rulers increased, the range of opportunities became narrower, and certain changes took place in its structure.

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